

EXPLORING THE CAUSES OF ENGLISH WRITING ANXIETY: A CASE STUDY UNDERGRADUATE EFL LEARNERS

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Abstract

This study intends to inquire about the causes and level of English writing anxiety among the EFL Learners. It also suggests the ways to overcome the issue with the aid of social cognitive theory. The data was collected with the help of two questionnaires. To know the level of anxiety, second language writing anxiety inventory was used (SLWAI). It consisted of twenty items which pointed out level of anxiety on SPSS (Statistical Procedure Social Sciences), software. The participants of study were 300 male and female students without mentioning gender. The participants were B. A and B.Sc. students. The results showed that participants had high level of writing anxiety, and the most prominent was cognitive anxiety. The discussion part of the study conferred with the help of social cognitive theory that how to overcome the writing anxiety.

Keywords: Writing Anxiety, Anxiety Types, Language and Gender

Introduction

The community often shares English writing issues it is because of English language teaching is still on its initial stages and mostly the words used by teachers for writing anxiety are confusion, tension, reluctance etc. (Dar and Khan, 2015). With other skills in English language writing skills also got less consideration and thought to be secondary issue to speaking. Students are not thought to be good writers in English language at college level. Writing is not liked by the people in our society. The students in colleges have the educational background of various schools. Mostly they are from the Urdu medium school. For that they cannot perform well in English language skills and especially speaking and writing. That is why they have English writing anxiety. So, whenever students are assigned task of writing they feel worried, tense and anxious. This uncomfortable state leads them towards inability. They feel fear of writing any kind of draft. This writing anxiety is the obstacle in producing skillful writers. Actually, it is writing skill that give success to a person in any written part of examination such as competitive exam.

Literature Review

Anxiety from acquisition of foreign language is a matter of fear that is related to language skills, i.e. writing, speaking, reading and listening. No doubt FLA and SLA anxiety is normal issue and mostly expressed by the students but it has its own effects on the learning of

students and considered one the major hindering in learning foreign language, has inverse impact to achieve foreign language skills (MacIntyre and Gardner,1994).

Writing anxiety can be originating from the past experiences or it can be said that its mere fear of writing in foreign language. For that, Horwitz et al. (1986), also pointed out to a type of performance anxiety that starts from a fear of failure. This fear of failing in test is found usually in every school and this situation only occurs in L2 writing. In the English writing instruction class, it has been mainly elaborated that writing anxiety is the main cause to decrease the quality of writing among the students. For this reason, students' counter challenges in writing, most of the students may become tense and become less motivate to write, thus, this will stop them to write because of the anxiety. Moreover, the students who have high levels of anxiety might face difficulties in learning the foreign language (Al Sawalha & Foo, 2013).

Types of Writing Anxiety

According to Cheng (2004), there are three kinds of writing anxiety, cognitive, somatic and avoidance. Cognitive anxiety means mental stress that includes wrong contemplation, related with performance and about others views. Somatic anxiety is concerned with psychological effects, such as ill at ease and strain. In avoidance anxiety learners avoid to write.

Cognitive anxiety

Cognitive tension indicates back to the cognitive factor of tension experience, which includes less hopes with overall reworking and challenge approximately others belief. What could be the way the scholars make their writing may be tremendously encouraged with the aid of using expectation from different college fellows or trainer. For example, the trainer offers excessive expectancy and the scholars ought to obtain the excessive general from the trainer. It can have an effect on the scholars' writing due to the fact they may extra awareness on others expectation in place of their very own writing.

Somatic anxiety

Somatic tension refers to one's belief of the mental results of the nervousness incident, which includes fear and anxiety. Sometimes college students are feeling fear in excessive anxiety while they are beneath the time constrains and that they have now no longer determined some thought.

Avoidance anxiety

Avoidance tension can be defined as a sort of tension wherein the scholars keep away from writing. This is another factor of the stress occurrence as scholars do not achieve the writing grace or do now no longer do their writing task.

Previous Studies

Studies of writing anxiety reveal high to moderate levels of anxiety in undergraduate EFL learners. Kaygısı and Sonuçları (2019) found the L2 writing anxiety from high to moderate

level in their study participants. The research includes the native Turkish speakers studying at the undergraduate level. They used quantitative research method adopted SLWAI as used by (Cheng, 2004) and qualitative method consisting of open-ended questions and interviews. Undergraduate learners were opted, as they could write complete essays in their institutions and believed to be proficient in English language. They could demonstrate proficiency through their written essays. All the undergraduate students were given SLAWI and 257 among them were selected for the research. The other qualitative portion of the study had two classes with general academic averages (GAA), two with average GAA and other two with lowest GAA the questionnaires were handed over to them only when they had written the second drafts of their essays during the course of the five weeks period. It was due to the fact that the qualitative aspect could be adequately analyzed after two written drafts of the essays. The participants of the qualitative part were 89, who answered the open-ended questions in the questionnaire; 9 students also participated in interviews. The interviews gave a better response to the questions. The study pointed out high level of anxiety in EFL learners.

High level of English writing anxiety in students of an Indonesian educational institution were prevalent. A study conducted on students of the Islamic State College in East Java, Indonesia, followed to determine as to what extent the writing anxiety levels were high, moderate, and low in the students; and what were the factors of the writing anxiety (Umam, 2017). The researchers used two questionnaires SLWAI and CWAI these questionnaires were used by Cheng and Rezaei and Jafari respectively. 54% student had high and 44% had moderate level and 2% had low level of writing nervousness. The cognitive anxiety was dominant anxiety among the students. Somatization was the physical manifestation of the writing anxiety that was analyzed in the student, whereas avoidance behavior was any actions the students took to escape from difficult thoughts and feelings of English writing. This study is relevant in understanding English writing anxiety in ESL students and can be replicated with the addition of other variables. The variables could be the learning styles and learning strategies of the students to reduce English writing anxiety.

The study aimed at toward investigating the connection among writing tension and writing self-efficacy by (Salem and Dyyar, 2014). It also explored writing anxiety with writing self-efficacy among man and women. The pattern of the study consisted of ninety intermediate college students within the nation of Kuwait (forty-seven men and forty-three females). Writing anxiety scale and self-efficacy scale were used to check performance in writing skills. Results of the study confirmed that there was writing anxiety among college students both male and female. Furthermore, it has been observed that writing anxiety scale can be used as an interpreter of college students' (male) writing self-efficacy but not for female students.

It also has been noticed that there had been no such variations in male and female students regarding the writing and self-efficacy in English language. It appeared to be ordinary as male and female scholars of any institution can be afflicted by the equal difficulties of gaining knowledge. Therefore, they each go through writing tension with the equal degree. As it has been noted beforehand, writing tension adversely encouraged the

scholars' capacity to write down efficiently. The study of Abdel-Latif (2007) has explored connection between writing anxiety and self-efficacy

The descriptive studies investigated the extent of English writing tension with the aid of using (Hartono and Maharani, 2019). The respondents had been 38 undergraduate college students of English Literature application of a college in Semarang Central Java, Indonesia taking essay writing route which followed portfolios because the evaluation method. Data had been accrued with the aid of using closed questionnaires; the only turned into for gathering facts of English writing tension and the second one turned into for gathering facts of writing troubles confronted with the aid of using college students which can also additionally cause the tension arousal. The effects display that the scholars skilled an excessive stage of English writing tension and cognitive tension turned into the scholars suffered maximum. Gender doesn't have an effect on the extent of hysteria skilled with the aid of using the scholars; neither does the notion of writing difficulties. Grammar hassle will become the maximum mentioned-reason of hysteria accompanied with the aid of using vocabulary hassle and inadequate writing practice.

To lessen the tension, therefore, it advocated that writing instructors sufficiently cope with the problem of grammar and vocabulary in addition to offers college students with a variety of extra writing practices. This examine changed into performed with the targets to provide an account on writing tension of the EFL college students in Indonesia. The end result confirms the preceding research that maximum of Indonesian rookies be afflicted by an excessive stage of writing tension, and cognitive tension is the maximum dominant type. Though this form of phenomenon additionally takes place in different countries, interest and attempt to triumph over the mental kingdom want to be taken severely due to the fact tension influences negatively the end result of learning. Language teachers, specially writing teachers, want to expand their coaching technique so that scholars can absolutely workout their writing capacity snug without being an excessive amount of harassed through the outside elements as the expectancy and assessment of others on their writing products.

Questions of the Study

- 1) What is the level of English writing anxiety among the students of colleges at district Jaffarabad?
- 2) What could be the factors responsible for English writing anxiety of colleges at district Jaffarabad?

Theoretical framework

This study employed mixed method approach. Creswell (2002) defined the mixed method in the following words as analyzing a problem "both quantitative and qualitative" to understand the issue and to have literature review will be helpful to justify the problem. An appropriate determination of research graph is very necessary to be used to have a hold close on the subject matter underneath investigation. It effortlessly pares a way to get knowledge and understanding concerning the subject and its objectives. Following discipline lookup approaches are used in this study.

The researchers like Cheng (2004) kirmizi and kirmizi (2015) and Wahyuni & Umam, (2017) had also discussed the issue, they used the SLWAI (second language writing anxiety inventory), The researcher in this study also kept the same model to know the causes and level of writing anxiety.

The Sample of the Study

The participants opted from B.A and B.sc in degree colleges of district Jaffarabad enrolled in the session of 2020-21. Degree colleges of Usta Mohammad have been included.

Tools of the Study

The data collection process had questionnaires of SLWAI as used by Cheng 2004 to know the level of anxiety.

After collecting the data, the data of two questionnaires were processed with help of 5-point likert scale. SLWAI (second language writing anxiety inventory).

SLWAI questionnaire was divided into three parts, can be named as cognitive anxiety, somatic anxiety, and avoidance behavior. For the cognitive anxiety these items were used 1, 3, 7, 9, 14, 17, 20, and 21. The somatic anxiety consist of items 2, 7, 8, 13 and 15. Item numbers for avoidance behavior were 4, 5, 10, 12, 16, 18, and 22. Furthermore the items 1, 4, 7, 17, 18, 21, and 27 consisted of an inverted likert scale calculation system: the option “strongly agree” had value scale of 1, and vice versa.).

Threshold

The data of SWAI were divided into three categories as high, medium and low anxieties (Wahyuni & Umam, 2017). If the mean on the likert scale is 73.33 (73) there is High-level of anxiety, if the mean on the likert scale is lower than 58.67 (59) can be included in low level of writing anxiety and the medium level anxiety occurs when the mean on the likert scale is in between above the two.

Data Analysis Procedure

SPSS 2.0 (statistical analysis procedure social) was used to analyze the data. With help of this software data were analyzed based on the type of anxieties, namely cognitive, somatic, and avoidance behavior, and got their means as high, medium and low-level anxieties respectively.

Results

This part of study is consisting of two questionnaires. The data of the questionnaires were collected and analyzes in two ways. Firstly, tables were used to show the result and with these tables, secondly, each table has been described too. The collected data were presented and also analyzed in the form of level, types and causes of English writing anxiety.

Research question I

What is the level of English writing anxiety among the college students in district Jaffarabad?

Table 2 and 3 presents the level of anxiety generally.

SLWAI, Second Language Writing Anxiety Inventory, was the tool to know the levels of writing anxiety as it was mentioned in research methodology. This questionnaire is consisting of 22 items. The participants who scored above 65 that indicated high level of anxiety, and those who scored below 50 means they had low level of anxiety and score in between 65 and 50 indicates moderate level of anxiety. The summary of whole questionnaire can be seen in table 2 and 3.

Table No. 2

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean
Anxiety level	300	23.00	110.00	21922.00	73.0733

In Table 2 the descriptive statistics of the SLWAI has revealed a high level of ESL writing anxiety (Mean=73>65) among the student samples. The score range of SLWAI is 22 as minimum and 110 as maximum. The students scored from 23 to 110. The mean score is 73 that means the students had high level of writing anxiety which is more than 65.

Discussion. Table No.3

Descriptive Statistics					
Anxiety Level	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean
High	130	93.00	110.00	10895.00	97.2768
Low	78	23.00	45.00	2482.00	31.0250
Moderate	92	50.00	64.00	2239.00	58.9211

Table 3, shows the level of anxiety separately as high, low, and moderate. It is shown in the table the students had high level of anxiety, 130 students scored 93 to 110 and sum is 10895, the mean is 97.27 which is the highest level of anxiety. Among 300 students 78 students

scored from 23 to 45, the mean is 31 which showed low level of anxiety and 92 students had moderate level of anxiety, they scored from 50 to 64 mean of moderate level is 58.92.

Table No.4. Types of writing anxiety

Descriptive Statistics					
Anxiety Types	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean
Somatic Anxiety	300	7.00	35.00	6974.00	23.2467
Cognitive Anxiety	300	9.00	40.00	7969.00	26.5633
Avoidance behavior	300	7.00	35.00	6979.00	23.2633

The Table 4 had shown cognitive anxiety as the most dominant anxiety with a total value of 7969 and mean is 26.56, secondly avoidance behavior with a value of 6979, the mean value is 23.26 and thirdly somatic anxiety with a value of 6974 with 23.24 mean. The anxiety level of the students is determined by the total means of each type of anxiety.

Research Question 2

What could be the factors for English writing anxiety of colleges at district Jaffarabad ?

The students indicate linguistic issues and lack of self-confidence and fear of exam become main factors that cause students to be anxious when they write English composition. Moreover, that students were tens when they are asked to write in time bound situation. shows lack of writing techniques.

Discussion

The results of the study show that it has been observed that the anxiety which dominant among the students is cognitive anxiety in which the participants are concerned about their English writing skills they think that their skills are worse than others as they sense disturbing while their writing which might be noticed and get a bad score. Following Wahyuni and Umam (2017) and Rezaei and Jafari (2014), it's far linear that cognitive anxiety is the dominant hassle engaged through the scholars, the mean of cognitive anxiety is 26.5633. This is better than the alternative two. However, distinctive outcomes can be due to the distinctive contexts in which the scholars are being taught by the institutions. For different reasons, the causal elements among the scholars are especially distinctive. In Wahyuni and Umams study (2017), the elements which cause the scholars affected by excessive tension are loss of grammatical skills, or they may be disturbed while their writing

might be evaluated. Further, in Rezaei and Jafaris (2014), worry of instructor's poor remarks, low self-confidence, and bad linguistic information are the primary sources

Conclusion

The students go through a high degree of writing anxiety. A type of anxiety called cognitive tension which became the leading trouble that passes on to the students' intellectual components while experiencing tension. Participants experience trouble once they assume that their English composition is not as good as others, and they feel displeasure when their composition gets a bad rating. They are deficient in linguistic skills in writing English and command of writing strategies. The students indicate linguistic issues and lack of self-confidence and fear of exam become main factors that cause students to be anxious when they write English composition. Moreover, result indicates that students were tense when they are asked to write in time bound situation.

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